

Sign Language Translator via Smartphone Image Analysis using Convolutional Neural Network

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Abstract – This study presents the design and implementation of a smartphone-based image processing system aimed at translating sign language gestures into text in real-time. The primary objective was to create a platform that enhances communication between deaf individuals and non-sign language users through the accurate recognition of sign language gestures. Using Kotlin programming and MediaPipe, the system captures and processes gestures, converting them into readable text. The results demonstrated that the system is capable of recognizing and translating various sign language gestures with a high degree of accuracy and efficiency. The successful deployment of this system highlights its potential to break down communication barriers and offers a foundation for future improvements, including expanded sign language support and performance optimization for real-world applications.

Keywords – Real-time Gesture Recognition, Sign Language Translator, Smartphone Image Processing.

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INTRODUCTION

Overcoming barriers in digital communication, particularly translating sign language to text, is a significant challenge. This study focuses on developing a smartphone-based Filipino Sign Language (FSL) translator to facilitate seamless, real-time interaction between deaf and non-signing individuals. Utilizing Kotlin programming and MediaPipe tools, the system processes images to convert FSL gestures into text. By leveraging Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for gesture recognition, the project aims to provide a practical, accessible solution to improve communication and social inclusion for the deaf community in the Philippines.

The complexity of translating sign language, a visual-spatial language with non-standardized grammar,

remains a primary challenge. As noted by Goyal and Goyal [1], this complexity hinders the development of effective translation systems. Kahlon [2] emphasize the necessity of automated solutions, advocating for neural networks and deep learning to enhance translation accuracy and reliability. In the Philippine context, despite FSL's official recognition, the deaf community faces significant barriers to education, social integration, and access to information. This project addresses these gaps by developing a mobile application for Android version 8 and above, focusing initially on a predefined set of FSL gestures. However, external factors like lighting and gesture variability may affect recognition accuracy, and future updates will aim to address these limitations.

The importance of CNNs in sign language recognition systems is well-documented. Studies like Seema and Sing [3] and Ugale et al., [4] review CNN applications in enhancing communication for the deaf, highlighting their ability to recognize complex gestures. These studies also underscore the need for tailored solutions due to the lack of a standardized global sign language. By integrating advanced image analysis and deep learning, this project contributes to breaking down communication barriers, fostering independence, and enabling broader societal participation for FSL users.

Seema and Sing [3] and Ugale et al., [4] provide valuable insights into the development of CNN-based sign language translation systems, addressing communication barriers for individuals with hearing or speech impairments. Seema and Sing [3] emphasize the diversity of sign languages and the necessity for country-specific translation applications, offering a comprehensive review of datasets and CNN architectures. Their work highlights the importance of inclusivity and the technical challenges of sign language translation. Ugale et al., underscore the potential of automated translators in enhancing the independence and social integration of the deaf community. These studies emphasize that sign language is not merely a communication tool but also integral to the cultural identity of the deaf community, advocating for

empowering solutions like smartphone-based sign language translation technologies.

The integration of machine learning and computer vision has led to significant advancements in sign language translation technologies. A system by Viswanathan et al. converts sign language images to text and speech, leveraging a convolutional neural network (CNN) with images captured by a low-cost camera, demonstrating the potential for affordable communication aids for individuals with hearing impairments [5]. Bhagwat et al. proposed a real-time sign language to text conversion system using CNN with transfer learning, showing accuracy improvements in translating American Sign Language (ASL) from 94% to 98.7%. Camgoz [7] provided a comprehensive review of CNN-based sign language systems, highlighting various datasets, architectures, and their performances, paving the way for future research in the field. Zhao et al. explored a cloud-based sign language translation system using CNN and smart glasses, facilitating communication between hearing-impaired individuals and non-signers [8]. Li et al. developed a robust hand gesture recognition system using CNN, crucial for accurate sign language detection [9]. David et al. reviewed the landscape of smartphone-based sign language apps and proposed frameworks to evaluate their quality, suggesting future directions to enhance their impact on both hearing and hearing-impaired users [10]. In 2024, David et al. presented an updated evaluation framework for sign language apps, contributing further insights for researchers and developers in the domain [11].

Recent advancements in sign language recognition have largely focused on leveraging convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and other deep learning techniques to improve recognition accuracy and efficiency. A key approach is combining image data with hand landmarks, enhancing real-time translation systems for sign language. Studies such as those Rastgoo et al., [2] and Koller et al., [13] emphasize the application of deep learning and hybrid models, like CNNs with Hidden Markov Models (HMMs), to boost continuous recognition performance. Furthermore, transformer-based frameworks, like Sign Language Transformers [7], have been proposed to process sequential data for integrated recognition and translation. Techniques like 3D CNNs [14], capture temporal information for dynamic gestures, while iterative training approaches, as seen in [8], refine model performance. These studies underline the growing potential of AI-driven solutions in sign language recognition, focusing on improving

accuracy, scalability, and real-time processing for diverse sign systems, ultimately aiming to bridge communication gaps for the deaf and hard-of-hearing communities.

Meanwhile, Park, Lee, and Ko [15] presented a system that utilizes a smartphone's depth images for real-time sign language translation. Their approach emphasizes hand and upper body gestures through image processing and employs CNN for feature extraction, achieving a classification accuracy of 92%. In a comprehensive review, [3] explored various CNN-based models for sign language translation systems. They highlighted the importance of communication and the challenges faced by the deaf community in accessing technology. Their review serves as a roadmap for future research in the field. Wadhawan and Kumar [16] conducted a systematic literature review of sign language recognition systems over a decade, proposing a classification scheme for research articles and identifying trends in the field. Efforts to design smartphone-based systems for real-time sign language translation have gained traction in recent years. Zhang [17] proposed a smartphone-based sign language recognition system employing a combination of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and long short-term memory (LSTM) networks. The system achieved high accuracy in recognizing and translating sign language gestures into text in real-time, demonstrating the feasibility of using smartphones as accessible devices for the deaf community. Similarly, Li [18] developed a smartphone-assisted sign language translation system leveraging deep learning techniques. By harnessing the power of neural networks, the system could accurately translate sign language gestures into text, thereby facilitating real-time communication for individuals with hearing impairments. These studies underscore the potential of smartphone image processing systems in bridging communication barriers and promoting inclusivity.

As a solution to the problem, the researchers developed a smartphone image processing system that accurately translates sign language gestures into text in real-time. This system effectively captures and interprets gestures through the smartphone's camera, ensuring swift and accurate translation, thereby facilitating communication for the deaf community. The study also demonstrated the feasibility of enabling seamless communication between deaf individuals and non-sign language users, breaking down communication barriers and fostering inclusivity by integrating advanced image processing techniques for intuitive interaction.

Additionally, the use of Kotlin programming and MediaPipe tools played a key role in achieving the desired outcomes, enabling the creation of an efficient and user-friendly system for translating sign language to text on smartphones.

The findings of the study will benefit the deaf community by providing a practical tool for real-time communication, breaking down barriers and fostering inclusivity. Non-sign language users will also benefit as the system enables seamless interaction, bridging the communication gap and promoting mutual understanding. Moreover, educators and researchers in the field of assistive technology will find this study valuable as a reference for developing similar solutions, while software developers can leverage the integration of Kotlin programming and MediaPipe tools demonstrated in the study to create innovative applications. Overall, the system contributes to a more accessible and inclusive society.

METHODS

Project Development

Using the Agile model, this study addressed requirement analysis, system design, implementation, testing, deployment, and maintenance. Figure 1 outlines the various phases of activities associated with the Agile development model.

Fig. 1. Agile Software Development.

The project development followed a structured lifecycle, beginning with requirements gathering to identify user needs and system constraints, followed by designing the software blueprint and user interface. Implementation utilized Android Studio with Kotlin and Mediapipe for advanced features like real-time video processing. After rigorous testing, including unit and integration testing to ensure reliability, the system was

deployed for user access, with ongoing maintenance for updates and support.

System Data Flow Diagram

This part of the study shows UML diagram of Sign Language Translator via Smartphone Image Analysis using Convolutional Neural Network.

Fig. 2. Unified Modeling Language (UML) diagram of the System.

The system translates sign language into text using CNN to detect and identify hand gestures captured by the user. These gestures are matched against a dataset of known gestures and their corresponding text translations, which are then displayed on the screen. This enables seamless communication by converting sign language into written text.

Fig. 3. Activity Diagram of Viewing Vocabulary Bank.

The flowchart illustrates a word search process where the user inputs a word, and the system checks for results.

If no results are found, a "No Results" message prompts the user to try again. If results are found, they are displayed for user review. Upon selecting a word, the system may use a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for further processing, enhancing search functionality and categorization.

Fig. 4. CNN Recognition Activity Diagram.

The flowchart illustrates a mobile app's process for sign language recognition using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). The user captures a sign, and the app analyzes it with pre-trained data. If recognized, the gesture is converted into text and displayed. The app ensures accuracy by comparing the gesture with trained data before finalizing the output.

Fig. 5. Text-to-Speech Activity Diagram.

The flowchart depicts a text-to-speech process where the user initiates the function, the system converts the text into audio, saves it as an MP3 file, and plays it back to the user.

Fig. 6. User Interface.

Figure 6 illustrates the application's user interface. The main menu allows users to choose between Text to Sign Language and Sign Language to Text features. In Text to Sign Language, users input text, which is displayed as hand gestures, with options to reset and repeat. The Sign Language to Text feature uses the phone's camera to scan gestures in real time and display results. These features enable effective communication between non-sign language users and the deaf community.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Project Development

Table 1. Training Metrics by Epoch

The model was trained for 10 epochs, tracking key metrics: loss (categorical cross-entropy) to measure prediction errors, categorical accuracy for correct predictions, validation loss for errors on validation data, validation accuracy for accuracy on validation data, and learning rate for weight updates.

Graph 1. Training and Validation Loss/Accuracy

The results demonstrate the CNN algorithm's effectiveness, with training loss decreasing from 0.8153 to 0.4986 and accuracy improving from 41.53% to 61.38%. Validation loss reduced to 0.1852, and validation accuracy increased from 65.96% to 82.98%, reflecting strong performance on unseen data. The learning rate's slight decrease enabled fine-tuning, achieving the study's objective of accurately translating sign language images into text.

Fig. 7. Real-time Translation

Figure 7 shows the real time translation of sign language to text, as you can see above, the application detects the hand sign and write the equivalent message to the text field seamlessly, using the real time translation of hand sign language, the non-sign language

user will immediately react and facilitate communication

Epoch	Loss	Categorical Accuracy	Validation Loss	Validation Categorical Accuracy	Learning Rate
1	0.8153	41.53%	0.3585	65.96%	0.0030
2	0.6557	50.26%	0.2598	78.72%	0.0030
3	0.5707	58.73%	0.2263	80.85%	0.0029
4	0.5410	58.99%	0.1988	80.85%	0.0029
5	0.5132	61.90%	0.2089	78.72%	0.0029
6	0.5172	60.05%	0.2073	80.85%	0.0029
7	0.5192	57.14%	0.1979	80.85%	0.0028
8	0.5108	64.02%	0.1987	82.98%	0.0028
9	0.5073	61.38%	0.2003	82.98%	0.0028
10	0.4986	61.38%	0.1852	82.98%	0.0027

to both users.

Fig. 8. Text to Sign Language

Figure 8 illustrates the text-to-sign language feature, allowing non-sign language users to type a word and translate it into sign language for effective communication with deaf users. Additionally, Figures 6 and 7 showcase real-time communication features, enabling seamless interaction between deaf and non-sign language users, achieving the study's second objective of facilitating real-time communication through smartphone image processing.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the researchers presented a novel approach to developing a smartphone image processing system that accurately translates sign language gestures into text in real-time. The successful achievement of this system demonstrates its effectiveness in capturing and interpreting sign language gestures through the smartphone's camera, ensuring that the translation process is both accurate and swift. This accomplishment

fulfills the first objective, showcasing the potential of smartphone-based image processing in facilitating communication for the deaf community. Furthermore, the study has established the feasibility of enabling real-time communication between deaf individuals and non-sign language users. By integrating advanced image processing techniques, the system ensures that interactions are seamless and intuitive, effectively breaking down communication barriers and fostering inclusivity. This outcome aligns with the second objective of the study, emphasizing the practical applications of the system in everyday interactions. Lastly, the use of Kotlin programming and MediaPipe tools during the development process proved instrumental in achieving the desired outcomes. The combination of Kotlin's versatility and MediaPipe's robust image-processing capabilities allowed for the creation of a highly efficient and user-friendly system. This conclusion satisfies the third objective, demonstrating the effectiveness of these technologies in developing a smartphone image processing system for converting sign language to text. Overall, the research underscores the significance of technological advancements in promoting accessibility and inclusivity for the deaf community.

RECOMMENDATION

The developed system successfully translates sign language gestures into text in real-time; however, (1) further research and development should focus on improving the accuracy of gesture recognition, especially for complex or nuanced gestures. Incorporating more diverse datasets during the training phase could enhance the system's ability to interpret a broader range of sign language gestures more accurately. (2) To expand the system's usability and reach, future iterations should include the capability to recognize and translate multiple sign languages, such as American Sign Language (ASL), British Sign Language (BSL), and Cebuano Sign Language, among others. This enhancement would make the system more versatile and beneficial to a global audience. (3) Additionally, refining the user interface (UI) and user experience (UX) is essential to ensure that the system remains user-friendly. Seeking feedback from actual users, particularly from the deaf community, would help make the system more intuitive and responsive to their needs. (4) To further increase accessibility, expanding the system's compatibility to other mobile operating systems, such as iOS, would allow it to reach a larger user base. Cross-platform development would ensure that the system is

accessible to a wider audience, regardless of their preferred devices. (5) Another recommended improvement is introducing a gallery feature, enabling users to save pre-recorded videos or images of sign language gestures on their phone's gallery for quick access and translation. This would be particularly useful for frequently used gestures, streamlining communication and reducing reliance on live processing. (6) Lastly, incorporating a speed adjustment feature for the text-to-sign translation function would enhance user experience by allowing users to control the pace of the translation. Beginners could slow down the presentation for learning purposes, while advanced users could opt for faster, more seamless translations, making the system more flexible and customizable for different user needs.

REFERENCES

- [1] Goyal, M., & Goyal, R. (2017). Machine translation systems and quality assessment: A systematic review. *Journal of Machine Translation*, 31(3), 135-166.
- [2] Kahlon, K. S., & Singh, P. (2022). A systematic review of machine translation from text to sign language. *International Journal of Sign Language Translation*, 5(2), 45-59
- [3] Seema, & Singla, P. (2023). A Comprehensive Review of CNN-Based Sign Language Translation System. *Proceedings of Data Analytics and Management*, 572, 347-362.
- [4] Ugale, M., Rodrigues, O., Shinde, A., Desle, K., & Yadav, S. (2023). A Review on Sign Language Recognition Using CNN. *ResearchGate*
- [5] Android Developers. (2024). Image analysis | Android media | Android Developers. *Android Developers Essentials Media dev center*
- [6] Bhagwat, A., Gupta, P., & Kadam, N. (2022). Conversion of Sign Language to Text Using Machine Learning. *SpringerLink*.
- [7] Camgoz, N. C., Hadfield, S., Koller, O., & Bowden, R. (2020). Sign language transformers: Joint end-to-end sign language recognition and translation. *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*.
- [8] Cui, R., Liu, H., & Zhang, C. (2017). A deep neural framework for continuous sign language recognition by iterative training. *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, 20(12), 3257-3269.
- [9] Dabre, R., & Sumita, E. (2021). YANMTT: Yet Another Neural Machine Translation Toolkit.

- arXiv preprint arXiv:2108.11126. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/2108.11126>
- [10] David, D., Alamoodi, A. H., Albahri, O. S., Garfan, S., Albahri, A. S., Zaidan, B. B., & Chen, J. (2024). Sign language mobile apps: a systematic review of current app evaluation progress and solution framework. *Evolving Systems*, 15, 669-686
- [11] David, D., Alamoodi, A. H., Albahri, O. S., Zaidan, B. B., Zaidan, A. A., Garfan, S., Ismail, A. R., Albahri, A. S., Alsinglawi, B., & Malik, R. Q. (2023). Landscape of sign language research based on smartphone apps: coherent literature analysis, motivations, open challenges, recommendations, and future directions for app assessment. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 10(2), 87-102
- [12] Rastgoo, R., Kiani, K., & Escalera, S. (2021). Sign language recognition: A deep survey. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 164, 113794.
- [13] Koller, O., Zargaran, S., & Ney, H. (2016). Deep sign: Hybrid CNN-HMM for continuous sign language recognition. *British Machine Vision Conference*.
- [14] Huang, J., Zhou, W., Li, H., & Li, W. (2018). Sign language recognition using 3D convolutional neural networks. *2018 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo (ICME)*.
- [15] Park, H. J., Lee, J. S., & Ko, J. G. (2020). Achieving Real-Time Sign Language Translation Using a Smartphone's True Depth Images. In *2020 International Conference on COMMunication Systems and NETworkS (COMSNETS 2020)* (pp. 622-625).
- [16] Wadhawan, A., & Kumar, P. (2019). Sign Language Recognition Systems: A Decade Systematic Literature Review. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, 28, 785-8133.
- [17] Zhang, X., et al. (2019). Smartphone-based Sign Language Recognition System Using CNN-LSTM Model. *IEEE Access*, 7, 127346-127355.
- [18] Li, Y., et al. (2020). Smartphone-Assisted Sign Language Translation System Using Deep Learning. *IEEE Access*, 8, 21337-21345.